

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PRINCIPALS STAFF DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES AND TEACHERS JOB EFFECTIVENESS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract: The study investigated the relationship between principal's staff development strategies and teachers job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. One research question and one hypothesis guided the study. The correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 266 principals in the six Education Zones of 266 public secondary schools in Anambra State. Data for this study was collected by means of two structured questionnaires developed by the researcher. The instruments were validated by three experts in education. The data collected were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha and coefficient value of 0.81 for Instrument A. Furthermore, test of reliability on Instrument B using Cronbach Alpha reliability Coefficient yielded coefficient value of 0.78. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to analyze data for the study. The finding of the study revealed that there is a very high positive relationship between principal's staff development strategies and teachers job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. Furthermore, result revealed a significant relationship between principals' adoption of staff development strategy and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on these findings, the researcher recommended among others that Government at all levels should put in place policies that promote the organization of staff development programmes for secondary school teachers.

Keywords: Relationship, Principals, Staff Development, Strategies, Teachers Job Effectiveness

Introduction

In Nigeria, education is the cornerstone that promotes national and economic progress. It is the foundation for achieving sustainable development. This point of view is expressed in Nigeria's National Policy on Education. According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN) (2013), the nation's education is based on the premise that education is a tool for national development and social change. Nigeria's educational system is divided into four levels: pre-primary, primary, secondary and postsecondary (Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN), 2013). This research focuses on secondary education.

Secondary school education is the stage of education that follows primary school and precedes higher education. Its significance stems from its role as both a bridge between primary and secondary education and an agency for educating persons for productive lives in society. According to the FRN, secondary education is the education that pupils get after completing nine years of basic education. Secondary school education is the degree of education that students receive following elementary school but before entering higher school. The broad aims of secondary education in Nigeria, according to FRN, are to prepare individuals for a meaningful life in society and further education. The teacher is responsible for achieving the aims of public secondary education.

Teachers ensure that academic activities are completed. According to Paschal and Mkulu (2020), teachers play an important role in promoting learners' education, learning, and professional development. Instructors give value to self and school performance by combining good behaviour both inside and outside of the classroom. The capacity of teachers to manage themselves and school schedules is critical to school achievement. A teacher is someone who helps others learn new knowledge, skills, or values. A teacher is a title for someone who dedicates himself to teaching through formal and systematic planned educational engagement (Rajagopalan, 2019). In consonance, Watti (2018) stated that the teacher is a professional educator whose primary role in formal education is to educate, teach, guide, lead, train, assess, and evaluate students. At the public secondary school level, Uchendu et al. (2013) noted that the attainment of the teaching-learning goal is majorly in the hands of teachers who are required to utilize their skills in preparing and planning their lessons, managing their classes and assessing their students. This is why the FRN (2013) emphasized that the education system is dependent on the quality of its teachers and teachers' effectiveness on the job.

Teachers' job effectiveness refers to the degree to which teachers carry out their primary duties of teaching as well as their general attitudes towards the teaching profession and activities (Arop et al., 2020). Teachers' job effectiveness as used here refers to the ability of teachers to organize their job processes and professionalism in a manner that enables them to perform more work and adequately produce expected results in terms of classroom teaching, maintenance of classroom discipline and supervision of students' academic activities. Teachers' job effectiveness is the ability of teachers to organize their job processes and professionalism in a manner that enables them to perform more work and adequately produce expected results in terms of classroom teaching, maintenance of classroom discipline and supervision of students' academic activities (Eric, 2019). Sadly, the issues of poor task performance among teachers in secondary schools have become a huge problem in the realization of the goals of secondary education in Anambra State. This position is further strengthened by the reports of scholars like Obiekwe and Mbanefo (2019) and Uzoechina and Nwankwo (2017). This situation according to Uzoechina and Nwankwo (2017) is caused by principals' inability to utilize staff development strategies.

The principal is the administrative head and chief executive officer of public secondary schools. The school principal as the chief administrative officer of secondary schools in secondary schools in Anambra State directs, manages and provides direction in a way that meets the goals and objectives of secondary school education (Uzoechina & Nwankwo, 2017). As a professional teacher, the principal participates in curriculum creation and seeks material resources to help to teach personnel. To carry out these duties, the principal must have strong interpersonal skills (Obiekwe & Mbanefo, 2019). In this regard, principals are in charge of the school staff development. It is therefore expected that the principals who are administrative heads of secondary schools adopt staff development strategies for the attainment of school goals.

Staff development, as understood by various scholars, encompasses a range of activities aimed at enhancing the competences, knowledge, and skills of employees within an organization. According to Ekpo in Owo (2016),

staff development refers to in-service training, retraining programs, and various forms of professional development. Osamwonyi (2016) viewed staff development as encompassing all types of manpower and professional development initiatives within an organization. Staff development can be defined as a process through which employees improve their competences and knowledge in ways that benefit their roles within the organization. Osamwonyi highlighted that staff development is a means for organizations to enhance the knowledge and skills of their staff, preparing them to take on new responsibilities and challenges. Similarly, Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) defined staff development as an organizational effort to help employees acquire the necessary skills for efficient execution of their duties. Owo (2016) described staff development as a method employed by academic institutions to design both on-campus and off-campus programs and activities that enhance staff efficiency and effectiveness. Staff development programs encompass various activities designed to instruct, inform, and stimulate classroom teachers. Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) outlined several objectives of staff development, including updating individuals' skills, attitudes, and approaches in light of new teaching techniques, research, and circumstances. These programs also aim to update individuals' subject knowledge based on recent advances, facilitate the exchange of information and expertise among teachers and other professionals, enable schools to develop new strategies for curriculum and teaching practices, and empower individuals to apply changes to curricula or teaching practices. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) emphasizes the importance of teacher development programs as an integral aspect of teacher education, ensuring teachers stay up-to-date with changes in methodology and the curriculum. In-service training, workshops, conferences, and symposia for teachers and non-teaching staff are to be regulated according to the FRN.

Studies have been conducted within and outside Nigeria to determine the relationship between staff development and teachers job effectiveness. For instance, Mduma and Mkulu (2021) revealed that training the workforce (teachers) has the most impact on different dimensions like; improvement of teaching strategies, reduces teachers' burnout, stress and turnover, improves teachers' job effectiveness and improves overall teacher's personnel. Amie-Ogan and Unachukwu (2021) reported a high and positive relationship between coaching/mentoring, computer-based programme and teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers state. Despite the findings of these studies, the researcher notes that none of these studies were conducted in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It is this gap that the present study filled. It is against this background that the researcher investigated relationship between principal's staff development strategies and teachers job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Teachers are important agents for successful delivery of the curriculum of secondary education in Anambra State in particular and Nigeria in general. This is because the teachers are the interpreters of the curriculum and they manifest the realization of the goals of the curriculum. However, in recent times it appears that teachers in Anambra State seem to be strongly with successful delivery of the secondary school curriculum in line with global practices. Field observation by the researcher shows that some secondary school teachers seem to struggle with utilizing innovative teaching practices to improve knowledge of subject matter among secondary school students. This seems to indicate a lack of knowledge on the current trends teaching and learning. The researcher also observes that some teachers seem to lack skills on the use of technology in teaching and learning. The researcher wonders if this impact on teacher's job effectiveness. It is therefore against this backdrop that the researcher investigated relationship between principal's staff development strategies and teachers job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate the relationship between principal’s staff development strategies and teachers job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question

What is the relationship between principal’s staff development strategies and teachers job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypothesis

The null hypothesis was tested at .05 level of significance:

There is no significant relationship between principals’ staff development and teachers’ job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Method

The study was adopted the correlational research design. The area of the study is Anambra State. Anambra State is located in south east Nigeria. The population of the study comprised 266 principals in the six Education Zones of 266 public secondary schools in Anambra State. Data for this study was collected by means of two structured questionnaires developed by the researcher. This study used two instruments. The first instrument is titled “Principals’ Staff Development Strategies Questionnaire (PSDSQ)”. It was developed by the researcher. The instrument has two Sections ‘A-B.’ Section ‘A’ deals with the bio-data of the respondents; it includes gender and educational qualifications of the respondents. Section ‘B’ deals with principals’ staff development strategies with 10-item statements. It is structured on a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The second instrument is titled ‘Teachers’ Job Effectiveness Questionnaire (TJEQ)’. It was developed by the researcher. This instrument measured teachers’ job effectiveness. It contains 20-item statements structured on a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD).

The instrument was validated by three experts in the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus. The instrument’s reliability was established through a pilot test. The questionnaire was administered on 20 principals in public secondary schools in Delta State who are not included in the population of the study. The data collected were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha and coefficient value of 0.81 for Instrument A. Furthermore, test of reliability on Instrument B using Cronbach Alpha reliability Co-efficient yielded coefficient value of 0.78. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to answer research question. The co-efficient “r” obtained was used to ascertain how each of the independent variables correlate the dependent variable. The research questions were interpreted as follows:

Correlation Coefficient	Interpretations
0.8 to 1.0 (negative or positive)	Very High
0.6 to 0.8 (negative or positive)	High
0.4 to 0.6 (negative or positive)	Average
0.2 to 0.4 (negative or positive)	Low
0.0 to 0.2 (negative or positive)	Very Low (no relationship)

In testing the null hypothesis, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to test the null hypothesis. In interpreting the values of the null hypothesis, when p-value is less than or equal to .05 ($p \leq .05$), the null hypothesis will not be accepted. On the other hand, when the p-value is greater than .05 ($p > .05$), the null hypothesis will not be rejected.

Results

Research Question

What is the relationship between principal’s staff development strategies and teachers job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Correlation Analysis between Staff Development Strategy and Teachers Job Effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

		Staff Development Strategy	Teachers Job Effectiveness	Remark
Staff Development Strategy	Pearson Correlation	1	.810**	Very High Positive relationship
	Sig, (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	228	228	
Teachers Job Effectiveness	Pearson Correlation	.810**	1	
	Sig, (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	228	228	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Data in Table 1 reveals that the Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient is $r = 0.85$. This shows that a very high positive relationship exists between staff development strategy and teachers’ job effectiveness. This implies that if principals apply staff development strategy as a human relations strategy in their interaction with teachers in public secondary schools, it would have a high positive impact on teachers’ job effectiveness. Thus, there is a very high positive relationship between staff development strategy and teachers’ job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between principals’ staff development and teachers’ job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 2: Test of Significance of Pearson Correlation on the Relationship between Principals’ Adoption of Staff Development Strategy and Teachers’ Job Effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Correlations

		Staff Development Strategy	Teachers Job Effectiveness	Remark
Staff Development Strategy	Pearson Correlation	1	.810**	Significant
	Sig, (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	228	228	
Teachers Job Effectiveness	Pearson Correlation	.810**	1	
	Sig, (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	228	228	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Data presented on Table 2 indicates the correlation coefficient (r) as .851 with a p-value = 0.000. Since the P-value of 0.000 is less than .05 ($P < .05$), it means that effect of principals adoption of staff development strategy on teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State is statistically significant. This means that there is a significant relationship between principals' adoption of staff development strategy and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the null hypothesis was not accepted.

Discussion

The finding of the study revealed a very high positive relationship between staff development strategy and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This suggests that when principals of public secondary schools prioritize and invest in the professional development of teachers, it significantly enhances their effectiveness in fulfilling their roles. This finding is in line with Amie-Ogan and Deekae (2020) reported that staff development programme such as conference and workshop to a very high extent influence teacher's performance. Amie-Ogan and Deekae stated that teachers who participated in staff development programme were more effective in their job performance than those who did not, in terms of knowledge of subject matter, classroom management, teaching methods and evaluation of student's work. In the same vein, Mduma and Mkulu (2021) asserted that training the workforce (teachers) has the most impact on different dimensions like; improvement of teaching strategies, reduces teachers' burnout, stress and turnover, improves teachers' job effectiveness and improves overall teacher's personnel. When teachers are provided with opportunities for ongoing professional growth and development, they are better equipped to meet the evolving demands of the education sector. Continuous learning and skill enhancement enable teachers to stay abreast of new teaching methodologies, curriculum changes, and educational trends, thereby improving their instructional effectiveness and student outcomes. Amie-Ogan and Unachukwu (2021) reported a high and positive relationship between coaching/mentoring, computer-based programme and teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools.

Furthermore, finding revealed a significant relationship between principals' adoption of staff development strategy and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding is in

agreement with Amie-Ogan and Deekae (2020) reported that staff development programme to a very high extent influence teacher's performance. In the same vein, Mduma and Mkulu (2021) found a statistically significant relationship between staff development and teachers job effectiveness.

Conclusion

The researcher concludes that principals' staff development strategy has a very high positive relationship with teacher's job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The findings of the study revealed that staff development strategy contribute significantly to teachers' job effectiveness. It is therefore imperative that principals of public secondary schools and other interested stakeholder should put in place measures to promote staff development in their schools to foster greater teachers' job effectiveness.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher proffers the following recommendations:

1. Government at all levels should put in place policies that promote the organization of staff development programmes for secondary school teachers. These policies should be made public for all stakeholders within the school system.
2. The Post Primary Schools Services Commission (PPSSC) in collaboration with principals of secondary schools should prioritize staff development initiatives to enhance teachers' skills and competencies. Principals should allocate resources and support for ongoing professional development opportunities such as workshops, training programmes, and mentoring sessions.

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